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Lectures

The Eshed-Dinoor Powdery mildew collection and its contribution to genetic studies of host-pathogen interaction at the primary center of origin of wheat and for long-term studies on crop resistance

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Israel and its vicinity constitute a center of diversity of domesticated wheat species (*Triticum aestivum* and *T. durum*) and their sympatrically growing wild relatives, including wild emmer wheat (*T. dicoccoides*). A collection of wheat powdery mildew (*Blumeria graminis f. sp. Tritici*, hereafter *Bgt*) isolates was established by N. Eshed in 1985, and was maintained and studied by A. Dinoor for four decades. The collection (n=61) was used for: (1) investigating differentiation within the *forma specialis* and (2) identification and genetic mapping of new powdery mildew resistance genes. Virulence and genetic characterization divided the *Bgt* collection into two distinct groups, those from domesticated hosts and those from wild emmer wheat, although the results do not support the existence of a separate *f.sp. dicocci*. In addition, isolates from the Eshed-Dinoor collection were used for the identification of new genetic resources of powdery mildew resistance from the wild and from the domesticated pool following wide screening of diverse wheat germplasm. This has led over the years to extensive genetic research and to the isolation of new resistance genes and alleles. Retrospectively, this research widened our understanding of the wheat powdery mildew patho-system at the primary center of origin and diversify the available genetic pre-breeding tool-box in efforts to improve future crop resistance.

Aerial journey of pycnidiospores: A new dimensions of disease outbreaks.

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The fungal *Botryosphaeriaceae* family includes many pathogens of woody plants that are known to disperse through the air for long distances *via* sexual ascospores and for shorter distances *via* water-splashed asexual pycnidiospores. However, the rarely reported sexual stage has never been found in Israel, while airborne dispersal is commonly found. Therefore, long-distance fungal dispersal should be associated with pycnidiospores, which are known to disperse by water splashes. This research aimed to elucidate the mechanisms behind pycnidial burst and long-distance dispersal of pycnidiospores of *Botryosphaeriaceae*. A strong correlation was found between the pathogenicity of *Botryosphaeria* and high seasonal relative humidity (RH). Indeed, high RH leads to pycnidial burst, while pycnidiospore dispersal was linked to decreasing RH along the day. Wind tunnel experiments revealed that pycnidiospores were carried farther as humidity levels and wind velocity increased over time. The mechanism of pycnidial burst is driven by high osmolyte molarity (sugars and glycerol), resulting in an osmotic pressure of 4.18 atmosphere. Based on these findings, we propose a mechanism for pycnidiospores release: in high RH, moisture permeates in the closed pycnidia and mixes with pycnidial sap, consequently increasing osmotic pressure that triggers pycnidial burst and pycnidiospores release. As the pycnidial sap and pycnidiospores dry, the wind drives their dispersal. We also found that the pycnidiospore release is a global mechanism that occurs in various *Botryosphaeriaceae* species on various tree species. These findings could alter our comprehension of fungal disease ecology and develop new strategies for epidemic disease management.

"What causes almond leaves to drop before the trees are shaken for harvest?"

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Almond trees in Israel are affected by various leaf diseases caused by fungal pathogens such as *Tranzschelia discolor*, *Polystigma amygdalinum*, and *Alternaria alternata*, which can lead to leaf shedding. These pathogens are widespread in almond-growing regions, but their prevalence, severity, and impact vary by area, season, and orchard. To combat these diseases, growers apply fungicides against all potential pathogens. However, despite up to twelve sprays per season, there have been many reports of treatment failures, resulting in leaf drop and crop damage. The reasons for this ineffectiveness remain unclear. We hypothesized that failures in controlling leaf drop stems from using unsuitable fungicides for specific pathogens in the orchards. The long-term goal of our research is to develop an optimal strategy to prevent leaf drop caused by leaf pathogens. In 2024, we conducted six experiments in five orchards in northern and central Israel using the leaf disease-susceptible Um El-Fahm variety. Various fungicides with different active molecules were applied starting in early May, before disease symptoms appeared, and continued until just before tree shaking for harvest. The only disease observed was almond leaf spot, with most pesticides showing little effect. Analysis of the findings led to an interesting possible explanation regarding the factors encouraging leaf drop.

Validation of a Decision-Support System named 'Tvazit' for Management of Peacock Spot Disease in Olive Trees

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The olive sector is considered to be the largest orchard industry in Israel, encompassing approximately 34,000 hectares of olive groves. Peacock spot disease in olives is caused by the hemibiotrophic pathogenic fungus *Venturia oleaginea*. Infected leaves drop prematurely, and in severe infestations, the tree appears to be in a state of defoliation. The common practice for disease suppression in Israel involves applying fungicide, often requiring 5–8 sprays per season. Despite the high frequency of sprays in susceptible olive varieties, severe disease outbreaks are occasionally observed in the treated groves. As part of David Ygzao's master's thesis, a decision-support system (DSS) named 'Tavazit' was developed for managing the disease. The system integrates daily minimum temperature data and precipitation quantity during the rainy days to optimize the timing of pesticide applications on the highly susceptible 'Souri' variety. During the 2023/24 season, we evaluated the effectiveness of the system in four experiments conducted in 'Souri' olive orchards in central and northern Israel. According to the system's recommendations, one or two sprays were applied at appropriate times in each experiment. Analysis of the findings revealed that implementing fungicides according to the 'Tavazit' system significantly reduced disease progression and leaf drop in treated trees compared to the untreated control trees. The impact of using the system, on yield production, was also examined, demonstrating a significant increase in yield (two fold or more) in the treated trees. The primary conclusion of this study is that the 'Tavazit' system can be effectively used to manage peacock spot disease in highly susceptible olive tree varieties.

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Thermotolerance of *Plasmopara viticola* and disease management strategy for controlling summer epidemics of grape downy mildew

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Epidemics of grape downy mildew caused by *Plasmopara viticola* are frequent and severe globally, including in Israel. Spring outbreaks are linked to rain events. Unlike other regions, severe summer epidemics have recently occurred in Israel without summer rains. Controlling summer outbreaks is challenging and may lead to leaf defoliation and yield loss. The sources of inoculum and environmental conditions driving such summer outbreaks remain unclear, hindering effective control. Climate change has enhanced the thermotolerance of the pathogen. High temperature (>38°C) is no longer suppressive to the disease as it was a few years ago. This study investigated the thermotolerance of the pathogen and searched for effective management strategies against summer epidemics. Monitoring disease development revealed that asymptomatic infected leaves might be responsible for the summer epidemics. Laboratory experiments revealed that thermotolerant *P. viticola* isolates infected leaves at 32°C and sporulated at 40°C, whereas wild-type isolates infected at 26°C, but failed to sporulate at 40°C. Field trials aimed to control summer epidemics included preventing spring infections, intervening during the transition period, and targeting summer outbreaks. Spring fungicide sprays reduced disease by 85–95%. Systemic fungicides applied during the transitional period (late spring) decreased disease incidence and severity on mature leaves by 82–92% and 91–100%, respectively. Summer sprays, directed by humidity and temperature thresholds, reduced incidence and severity by 40–50% and 90–95%, respectively, while preventing 95% of leaf defoliation compared to untreated vines. This study emphasizes the need for region-specific, adaptive strategies to combat thermotolerant downy mildew in vineyards under warming climate conditions.

Studying tomato brown rugose fruit virus longevity in soil and virion susceptibility to pH treatments helped improve virus control by soil disinfection

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The tobamovirus Tomato brown rugose fruit virus (ToBRFV) is an economically important plant pathogen in tomato cultivation worldwide. Its virion is characterized by high stability which allows for its preservation in plant debris, on surfaces and in soils following a contaminated growth cycle. Deepening our understanding of ToBRFV preservation in soils is important to find solutions for the prevention of soil-mediated contamination, especially in monocultural cultivation. To that end, soils naturally contaminated with ToBRFV were collected in a pile for experimental purposes. The pile was divided into two treatments: dry and wet with a cover crop. The soil piles were sampled in different time intervals and used as growth medium for root-truncated tomato plants. Infection potential in the wet soil pile was retained up to 205 days post soil collection. Simultaneously, ToBRFV virion stability was studied using a virion preparation tested in solutions with a pH range of 1.0-12.0. The solutions were tested for infective potential in a bioassay using tobacco plants, RT-PCR was performed to determine genome integrity and microscopy was utilized to determine virion morphology. The data collected showed that infection potential, genome integrity and virion morphology were intact in a pH range of 1.0-10.0. These results led to the creation of a soil disinfection protocol using a Cl-TSP solution with a pH of 11.6, above the 10.0 threshold. The disinfection protocol profoundly reduced soil-mediated ToBRFV infection of tomato plants compared the non-treated control, indicating that virion stability studies can inform virus management solutions at the field level.

Improvement of tobamovirus resistance in tomato plants by modulating the activity of the *Tm-2²* gene

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Plant viruses of the *Tobamovirus* genus cause significant damage to various crop species. The tomato brown rugose fruit virus (ToBRFV) is an emerging virus that severely affects the local and global tomato industry. ToBRFV overcomes the *Tm-2²* resistance (R) gene, which has protected tomatoes from tobamoviruses for over 60 years. *Tm-2²* encodes a plant immune receptor that recognizes the tobamovirus movement protein (MP) and triggers a defense response to limit virus spread. Previous work in our laboratory showed that *Tm-2²* fails to recognize the ToBRFV MP, rendering it ineffective against this virus. To identify improved *Tm-2²* variants with potential ToBRFV protection capacity, a *Tm-2²* mutant library was generated and screened. Notably, three *Tm-2²* variants (*DE311*, *DE872* and *DE905*), activate plant immune response when co-expressed with the ToBRFV MP in *N. benthamiana* leaves. However, the ability of these *Tm-2²* variants to confer ToBRFV resistance plants has never been tested in tomato. In this work transgenic tomato plants were generated overexpressing either the wild-type *Tm-2²* or its mutant variants *DE311* and *DE905* under the 35S promoter. ToBRFV resistance was further tested by mechanical inoculation experiments. Overexpression of wild-type *Tm-2²* did not enhance resistance to ToBRFV. In marked contrast, overexpression of *Tm-2²* mutants *DE311* and *DE905* enhanced ToBRFV resistance by decreasing viral RNA levels and reducing disease symptoms. However, these mutants did not provide ToBRFV immunity. This research improves our understanding on the role of *Tm-2²* in tobamovirus immunity and suggests potential strategies to modify its function for ToBRFV resistance.

Make it grow: *Pseudozyma aphidis* promotes plant growth

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Increasing global population requires higher food supply while avoiding the use of harmful products in agriculture. The use of beneficial microorganisms is an Eco-friendly approach to reduce the use of harmful agricultural products. We isolated a unique *Pseudozyma aphidis* strain (L12) that has shown anti-microbial and plant growth promoting activity. *P. aphidis* is a yeast like dimorphic fungus related to the phytopathogenic fungus *Ustilago*. Unlike its relative, *P. aphidis* is not only non-pathogenic but rather beneficial to the host plant. *P. aphidis* secretes compounds that were found to have bioactive properties. We isolated the fraction with plant growth promoting activity and tested it on different plants. Tomato, melon and corn plants treated with our extract exhibited enhanced growth parameters and the tomato plants produced higher and better-quality yield. The pharmacological parameters of our fraction were tested and GCMS analysis was conducted to identify potentially bioactive compounds. We found that it contains siderophores and auxin like derivatives. Genomic analysis (RNAseq) of juvenile tomato plants treated with our extract was carried out in order to identify the growth mechanisms engaged by our extract. The transcriptome data revealed that our extract prompts mainly biological pathways related to plant growth and development. Characterization of plant growth promoting activity, compounds and the mechanisms involved in interaction of beneficial microorganisms such as *P. aphidis* with host plants will enrich our knowledge. The data and insights from our research can promote the development of green products that can reduce harmful agricultural products usage.

Avoiding disease onset in Agri photovoltaic (APV) growth systems

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APV combines solar photovoltaic systems with agricultural practices, offering benefits such as renewable energy generation, efficient land use, and potential mitigation of climate impacts. In an APV facility established in 2021 at Bar Ilan University, Israel we investigated for three years the effect of the shading imposed by the solar panels (26% coverage area) on the photosynthetic irradiation (400-700 nm) captured by the plants, plant growth, crop yield and onset of foliar diseases of tomato, potato, sunflower, corn and pineapple. We also measured the electricity generated by the solar panels. The results showed a significant reduction in yield in the plants growing under the panels but not in plants growing away from them. Such plants also became infected with fungal diseases such as late blight in potato, powdery mildew in tomato and powdery mildew in sunflower. The sensors installed in the field revealed that the temperature and relative humidity that prevailed under the panels were conducive for onset of the above diseases. We suggest avoiding growing vegetable crops under the panels but recommend growing pineapple which was found to provide excellent yield under the panels. The income obtained from the electricity generated by the panels provided an extra net income of 1200\$ per dunam per season as compared to conventional agriculture. We conclude that APV is a profitable technology. It supports the governmental decision to make sun energy the primary source of renewable energy in Israel by 2030.

The effect of CGMMV on postharvest quality and storability of cucumber fruits

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Cucumber (*Cucumis sativus* L.) is one of the most widely cultivated and essential crops worldwide. In intensive agriculture, cultivation of cucumber plants in a greenhouse, the agro-technical activities expose the plant to infection by the *Tobamovirus* cucumber green mottle mosaic virus (CGMMV) can lead to a decrease in cucumber yield, yet little is known about its impact on the postharvest quality of the fruit. To examine the effect of CGMMV infection on the quality and storability of cucumber fruit after harvest, cucumber fruit were harvested from CGMMV-infected and non-infected plants. Inoculation of plants at later development stages led to the production of marketable fruit that showed no apparent differences in quality compared to non-infected fruit, at harvest. Nevertheless, the quality of fruit after cold storage (4°C for 10 days) was significantly affected by CGMMV infection. Infected fruit were more susceptible to chilling injuries, as evidenced by the degradation of fruit peel chlorophyll, increased ion leakage, elevated levels of Malondialdehyde, and higher values of auto-luminescence, which demonstrated enhanced lipid peroxidation and membrane damage. Furthermore, CGMMV-infected fruits stored at 15°C were significantly more susceptible to gray mold disease caused by *Botrytis cinerea*. Transcriptome analysis of the fruits at harvest indicated upregulation of genes encoding for regulatory factors associated with ethylene biosynthesis, phenylpropanoids metabolic pathways, and WRKY, suggesting the involvement of several pathways in mediating the differential physiological response of the CGMMV-infected fruits to postharvest insults. These results indicate viral infection of fruit as an additional, previously unappreciated factor that may shorten fruit storability and should be taken into account as a potential driver of fruit deterioration, leading to losses of fresh produce after harvest.

Compositional variances in cuticular lipids of wild and domesticated barely leaves and their impact on plant-environment interactions

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One of the oldest cereal crops, barley is thought to have been domesticated ~ 8000 years ago, in the Fertile Crescent. In this study, we explored the overlooked contribution of cuticular lipid metabolism to barley domestication by comparatively characterizing wild and domesticated barley variants. We revealed substantial phenotypic variances in plants' overall morphology and in vegetative and reproductive tissues. Multiple microscopic approaches combined with gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) metabolite profiling indicated that wild barley leaves are more densely covered with epicuticular waxes compared to domesticated leaves with distinct compositions, but both variants contain a similar cuticle ultrastructure. Gene expression assays corroborated these observations showing higher transcript expression of key epicuticular wax biosynthetic genes in wild barley leaves, but similar expression patterns of cutin biosynthetic genes in leaves of both cultivars. Previous evidence claimed that barley leaf epicuticular waxes shape the interactions with *Blumeria graminis* f.sp. *hordei* (*Bgh*), the causal agent of powdery mildew in barely. However, *in-vivo* and *in-vitro* inoculation assays inferred that the disparate wax content and composition in wild and domesticated leaves had no apparent effect on *Bgh* pre-penetration processes. Altogether, our data provide novel insight into the compositional variances in cuticular lipids of wild and domesticated barley leaves and their impact on plant-environment interactions.

Knockout of *CsRDR1b* and *CsRDR1c* genes in *Cucumis sativus* mediated suppression of the PAL genes leading to hypersensitivity to virus and oomycete co-infection and reduction in phenylpropanoid biosynthesis

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Cucumber (*Cucumis sativus* L.) is one of the important vegetable crops in Israel and in the world. In recent years, we found that cucumber-mature plant collapse is caused by the co-infection of the *Tobamovirus* cucumber green mottle mosaic virus (CGMMV) and a necrotrophic pathogen *Pythium spinosum*. Enzyme RDR1 plays a crucial defense role against plant viruses by secondary amplifying viral double-stranded RNA in the gene-silencing pathway. Four RDR1 (*CsRDR1a*, *b*, *c1*, *c2*) genes were identified in cucumbers having different expression levels before and after infection by various viruses. Knockout of *rdr1b*, *rdr1c1* and *rdr1c2* by CRISPR/Cas9 caused exceptional susceptibility of *rdr1b* and especially *rdr1c1* and *rdr1c2* mutants to co-infection with CGMMV and *Pythium Spinosum* that led to 100% mortality of *rdr1c* mutants, 20% mortality of *rdr1b* mutants and 100% survival of cv. Ilan (WT). The transcriptomic analyses of non-infected mutants mediated suppressing the PAL and Peroxidase genes and reduced phenylpropanoid biosynthesis. We assume that there is an interaction between RDR1, PAL, and Peroxidase enzymes in plant pathogens' defense, and the suppression of these enzymes caused the hypersensitivity of *rdr1* mutants to co-infection.

Intra-species Interaction and Relationship with *Fusarium verticillioides* in the Maize Wilt Late Disease Agent, *Magnaporthiopsis maydis*

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Maize late wilt disease, caused by the fungus *Magnaporthiopsis maydis*, poses a significant threat to susceptible crops. This study reveals that the population of *M. maydis* in Israel displays diverse levels of aggressiveness, which are unrelated to geographic distribution. Additionally, some subspecies groups specialize in growth disruption, while others cause wilting, indicating biotrophic and necrotrophic variation. While weak pathogenic strains affected the susceptible cultivar Prelude, the resistant cultivar Royalty was only impacted by highly aggressive isolates, resulting in a 7% reduction in growth and 11% mortality at harvest. Unexpectedly, a mixed inoculum of the two most virulent isolates during sprouting led to reduced disease severity. Still, by harvest, this trend reversed, and adding a weakly virulent strain to the mix caused a more severe reduction in growth (23%) and health (71%), with a high level of *M. maydis* infection. Compared to *Fusarium verticillioides*, another post-flowering stalk rot pathogen, *M. maydis* exhibited greater aggressiveness, with 40% plant survival and up to 1,000 times higher DNA levels. Co-inoculation of the two pathogens increased the number of healthy plants from 10% (for *M. maydis* alone) to 30%. Sequential infection with *F. verticillioides* first reduced symptoms and *M. maydis* infection, though plant growth remained poor. This study improves our understanding of the late wilt pathogen's complex inter- and intraspecies interactions and its destructive threat to maize crops.

Exocarp-specific expression of a fungal cutinase in tomato fruit causes cracking of the skin, and the formation of a suberized periderm that confers resistance to *Botrytis cinerea*

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The hydrophobic cuticle regulates the transport of water, gases and solutes, and constitutes a protective barrier against abiotic and biotic stresses. The tomato fruit emerged as a model for studying cuticle properties, yet the molecular mechanisms activated in this layer during interaction with pathogens are partially understood. Herein, we generated transgenic tomatoes that overexpress in an exocarp-specific manner a cutinase enzyme isolated from the fungus *Fusarium oxysporum* f.sp. *lycopersici*. This enzyme breaks down the ester bonds linking cutin monomers that built the cuticle, thus allowing the fungus to penetrate into the inner fleshy tissues. Light and electron microscopy demonstrated that the skin of transgenic fruits was fully cracked albeit these fruits deposited significantly thicker cuticles than those of wild-type fruits. Additionally, a suberized periderm was detected underneath the cracked skin. These observations were validated via gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) profiling. A series of *in vivo* and *in vitro* inoculation assays was performed to examine how these structural and biochemical alterations affected the ability of the necrotrophic fungus *Botrytis cinerea* to infect and penetrate transgenic fruits. Despite their cracked skin, transgenic fruits were surprisingly more resistant exhibiting smaller fungal hyphae diameter and minimal evidence of fungal penetration. Correspondingly, qRT-PCR assays delineated higher expression levels of *cutA* and *cutB* - the two key cutinases of *B. cinerea* responsible for the fungus penetration process. Overall, these findings shed light on the protective role of the fruit cuticle, and highlight the suberized periderm as an effective biochemical barrier against the infection of fungal pathogens.

Symphony of resistance: NLR expression in melon against multiple pathogens

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The majority of plant disease resistance (R) genes encode nucleotide-binding (NB) leucine-rich repeat (LRR) proteins (*NLR*). In this research, we focused on the *NLR* family in melon, identifying, annotating, and classifying 93 *NLRs*, of which 43 were full-length, containing all three domains: n-terminal domain, NB and LRR. Using large-scale qRT-PCR, we quantified transcripts of these 43 full-length *NLRs* along with selected defense-related genes involved in plant defense responses. The analysis was conducted in two multi-pathogen-resistant melon genotypes, PI414723 and MR-1, and a susceptible genotype, Charéntais-T, in response to five common pathogens: two potyviruses (*Papaya ringspot virus* [*PRSV*] and *Zucchini yellow mosaic virus* [*ZYMV*]) and three fungal pathogens (*Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *melonis* races 1 and 2, and *Podosphaera xanthii* race 1, the powdery mildew agent). Our findings revealed significant differences in *NLR* expression between resistant and susceptible genotypes. Some pathogens induced widespread gene activation, while others caused minimal changes. We identified *NLRs* linked to salicylic acid (SA)- and jasmonic acid (JA)-related pathways, with distinct expression patterns: some specific to one pathogen, others responding to related pathogens, and some linked to multiple pathogens. In the susceptible genotype, we observed unexpected upregulation of certain genes that suggested manipulation of host responses. Furthermore, *NLR* genes were predominantly upregulated, indicating that plants enhance defense by increasing *NLR* expression. Understanding *NLR* specificity, hormonal crosstalk, and their broader role in resistance will provide insights for improving plant immunity.

ER stress responses in *Bemisia tabaci* and their role in Tomato yellow leaf curl virus transmission

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Tomato yellow leaf curl virus (TYLCV), a Begomovirus transmitted by the silverleaf whitefly *Bemisia tabaci*, poses a substantial threat to tomato cultivation worldwide. While many molecular studies have examined how *B. tabaci* transmits TYLCV, the mechanisms involved in the insect's immune response to the virus remain poorly understood. Our study aimed to investigate the Endoplasmic Reticulum (ER)-associated immune responses in insects during TYLCV infection. The ER is a major organelle in the cell where stress responses such as autophagy and apoptosis are initiated upon pathogen infection. In order to explore the ER role in the virus-vector interactions, we identified three major ER stress sensor proteins: ATF6, PERK and IRE1, which reside on the ER membrane and initiate stress responses upon pathogen infection. Immunolocalization revealed higher expression and localization of these sensor proteins in viruliferous whiteflies compared to non-viruliferous ones, suggesting an active ER stress response. Ongoing inhibition studies aim to further determine whether these pathways play a direct role in modulating viral accumulation and transmission within the insect. Our findings highlight a possible role of the ER stress response in *B. tabaci*'s immune defense against TYLCV, offering potential targets for interfering with the virus transmission.

Resistance to fungicides in Apple Powdery Mildew: Insights and Eco-Friendly Alternatives

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Apple powdery mildew, caused by *Podosphaera leucotricha*, is a major threat to apple production worldwide, affecting leaves, flowers, and young fruits. Disease management primarily relies on chemical fungicides, including demethylation inhibitors (DMIs) and respiration inhibitors such as SDHIs and QoIs. Reduced fungicide efficacy has been documented worldwide. The intensive use of fungicides increases the risk of resistance development, even though no mutant *P. leucotricha* isolates have been confirmed to date. Israel's climate, characterized by occasionally rainy springs and dry summers, promotes powdery mildew development and necessitates frequent fungicide applications. This study examines the occurrence of *P. leucotricha* resistance to fungicides using field trials, laboratory experiments, and genetic analyses. Trials conducted in apple orchards in the Golan Heights revealed low efficacy (20–30%) for penconazole (DMI) and kresoxim-methyl (QoI) compared to the higher efficacy of trifloxystrobin (QoI). Laboratory bioassays involving leaf discs and isolates collected from infected leaves in the field showed EC₉₀ values of 30 and 75 ppm for penconazole and kresoxim-methyl, respectively, both close to the recommended field application rates. Trifloxystrobin, however, exhibited EC₉₀ values below 2.1 ppm. Genetic analyses did not detect mutations associated with DMI or QoI resistance, suggesting alternative resistance mechanisms. To reduce the use of fungicides, we examined the efficacy of fertilizers containing macro- and micronutrients. Greenhouse trials showed a 94–97% reduction in disease incidence, while orchard trials demonstrated 77–83% efficacy in reducing severity. This study provides the first insights into *P. leucotricha* resistance in Israel and highlights eco-friendly alternatives to conventional fungicides.

Identification of the volatile profile of microorganisms in soil crusts.

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Current methods for soil pathogen testing are time-consuming, expensive, and sometimes unreliable. In addition to secondary metabolites, microorganisms release a variety of small molecular weight volatile metabolites (mVOCs). These molecules are involved in both intra- and interspecies communication. In this study, we aim to identify the unique volatile profiles of soil fungi and algae, including pathogenic fungi, in order to develop a new, fast, efficient, and accessible method for pathogen detection in soil tests. Creating an initial database of the unique volatile profiles of these microorganisms will enable their identification in various soil samples. Preliminary findings have shown that varying concentrations of the fungus *Alternaria atra*, isolated from biological soil crusts, can be distinguished from natural soil using its specific volatile profile. For the study, we will isolate algae and fungi from biological soil crusts in the Nizzana dunes, followed by morphological and molecular identification. Using gas chromatography (GC), we will identify the volatile profiles of each isolated algae and fungus, which will form an initial database to help identify different species in natural soil samples. This approach may streamline pathogen diagnosis and identification, reduce testing costs, and improve agricultural and environmental management through early and accurate detection of harmful microorganisms. Ultimately, the results could lead to more targeted and environmentally friendly management practices, ensuring food security by providing a fast and accurate diagnostic system. This research has the potential to revolutionize current methods of soilborne pathogen detection and contribute to more resilient agricultural systems worldwide.

Development of an Azoxystrobin Slow-Release Clay Carrier Against the Maize Late Wilt Disease Agent, *Magnaportheopsis maydis*

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Late wilt disease significantly threatens maize production in Israel and other countries. The disease is caused by the soil- and seed-borne fungal pathogen *Magnaportheopsis maydis*, which, in severe cases, can lead to mortality from 60 days onward. The primary control method involves the use of resistant maize cultivars; however, these are challenged by virulent pathogen strains. This study evaluated a novel approach for disease management using the slow release of Azoxystrobin from clay carriers. Laboratory experiments tested various modified clays but found no improvement in the chemical absorbance. Therefore, raw Bentonite and Sepiolite clays were selected for further pot trials. Applying the new formulation in growth chamber pots, either as a seed coating or in the planting hole, resulted, after 20 days, in a significant shoot weight reduction (12–16%). However, qPCR analysis indicated a 76–99% pathogen root infection decrease in the seed-coated plants. In a full-season (78 days) greenhouse trial, adding the clay-Azoxystrobin formulations into the planting hole led to substantial increases in shoot and cob weight (210% and 175%, or more) compared to the infected control. Additionally, pathogen root infection was significantly reduced—by ca. 50% and 100% with the Sepiolite and Bentonite treatment. The new method tested here may protect maize plants during the critical stages of root colonization and establishment by *M. maydis*. It is cost-effective, adaptable to various cultivation practices, and, if combined with biological control agents, has the potential to mitigate resistance development and safeguard plants against other soilborne diseases under field conditions.

Early non-destructive detection of internal rots caused by *Alternaria alternata* in sweet pepper (*Capsicum annuum* L.)

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Sweet pepper (*Capsicum annuum* L.) is among the ten most produced vegetables in the world, with an annual production of approximately 38M tons. The FAO reports that pests and diseases account for 25% of agricultural crop losses, with *Alternaria alternata* being a significant cause of decreased yield in peppers. Field surveys and infection trials indicate that *A. alternata* can infect fruit during flowering, causing quiescent infection that result in high levels of internal rot in fruits from severely-infected commercial fields. This problem is common in pepper-growing countries and poses a significant challenge for postharvest management. Internal rot in peppers poses two major challenges. The first is identification: infected fruits often lack external signs, making it challenging to identify and remove them. Second, when the fungus grows in the placenta area, it produces mycotoxins that are toxic to human health. In addition, during storage, infected fruits may spread spores, infecting healthy fruits, increasing economic losses. Preliminary experiments show that the fungus penetrates the seed coat and reaches the endosperm, a lipid-rich tissue that likely serves as a nutrient source for the pathogen. Our study hypothesizes that lipid degradation releases volatile organic compounds (VOCs), the detection of those, resulting from lipid degradation or compounds produced as an immune response of the fruit, may allow a non-destructive detection of internal decay caused by *A. alternata*. In addition, a spectral detection method based on Raman spectroscopy will be developed to detect chemical changes associated with internal rot, offering another approach to improve early detection.

Effectidor II: A pan-genomic AI-based algorithm for the prediction of type-III secretion system effectors

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Machine-learning algorithms are widely used to predict type III effectors (T3E) in plant bacterial pathogens. We have previously developed Effectidor - a web server (freely available at <https://effectidor.tau.ac.il>), which classifies each ORF within a genome to either a T3E or not. The algorithm relies on features such as the presence of regulatory elements in the promoter, the amino-acid composition of the protein, and its sequence similarity to previously identified T3Es. Here we extended Effectidor to analyze pan-genomes (up to 400 genomes simultaneously). The joint information from hundreds of genomes provides more accurate predictions. It allows the inference of effectors' evolutionary dynamics across the pan-genome, e.g., identifying core T3Es, and clade-specific T3Es. In addition, the new version of Effectidor provides better annotation of the analyzed genomes, e.g., the subtype(s) of the encoded type III secretion systems (T3SSs). The minimal requirement to run the web server is a single genomic sequence. However, more accurate predictions can be obtained using advanced options, e.g., by including proteomes of closely related bacteria that do not encode a T3SS and by providing data on host proteomes. Furthermore, we demonstrate that Effectidor II identifies novel effectors based on the pan-genome, that were not identified in a run on a single genome.

Etiology of Postharvest Decay of Long-Term Stored Carrots and Development of Sustainable Control Measures

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The fungicide Rovral[®] (a.i.: Iprodione 50% v/v) was banned for use as a postharvest treatment of long-term cold-stored carrots (0–2°C for 6–10 months) in late 2020. As a replacement, Scholar[®] (a.i.: Fludioxonil 230 g/L) was registered and entered commercial use on January 2021. To prevent the potential development of resistance to Scholar[®], the goal of the present study is to elucidate the etiology of decay-causing pathogens of cold-stored carrots and develop integrated and sustainable decay management protocols. . A total of 101 fungal isolates were recovered from infected carrots collected from commercial cold storage facilities across Israel. Genetic identification was performed using ITS1 & 4 primers, followed by species specific primers for advanced identification. Koch's postulates were completed, and pathogenic isolates were evaluated for their aggressiveness to carrot at 5 and 16°C. Ten *Botrytis cinerea* (gray mold) and 11 *Sclerotinia sclerotiorum* (white mold) isolates were identified as most aggressive to carrot. Tolerance to Scholar[®] was recorded in both pathogens at 10 ppm in poisoned liquid medium; and one *S. sclerotiorum* isolate was highly resistant to both fungicides at 1000 ppm. *In-vitro* results were validated on inoculated carrot bioassays, indicating synergism between Scholar[®] efficacy and cold temperature (5°C). Ongoing research investigates the resistance mechanisms to fludioxonil in *B. cinerea* and *S. sclerotiorum* using molecular and physiological tools. Combinations of Scholar[®] with inorganic GRAS salts (CaEDTA and ammonium bicarbonate) are evaluated for efficacy to mitigate decay and reduce potential pressure of resistance build-up.

Identifying tissue specificity determinants of the tomato pathogen *Clavibacter michiganensis* through characterization of vascular and parenchyma-evolved clones

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The plant pathogenic bacterium *Clavibacter michiganensis* (Cm) is a vascular pathogen that infects both the xylem and parenchymatic tissues during different stages of the disease cycle. This study aims to determine if tissue adaptation influences Cm virulence. A preliminary tissue-specific experimental evolution was conducted, adapting 20 independent clone lineages to vascular or parenchymatic environments by passaging them in tomato stems or leaves. Phenotypic characterization of the evolved clones identified that most vascular-adapted clones displayed a reduction in virulence, which was unaffected in the parenchymatic-adapted clones. Considering that Cm vascular aggression is facilitated by systemic spread, we hypothesized that virulence reduction of the vascular-adapted clones results from altered tissue localization and systemic spread patterns. To test this, representative vascular- and parenchymatic-adapted clones were labeled with GFP and monitored for in situ localization within infected tissues and migration into distal regions of the plant from the site of inoculation compared to the wild type. While no biases were observed in xylem or parenchymatic preferences between the wild type and the adapted clones, we observed clear differences in distal migration patterns when bacteria were present. Similarly to the wild type, both vascular- and parenchymatic-adapted clones retained high populations throughout the main stem; however, the vascular-adapted clones displayed reduced leaf migration compared to the wild type, and the opposite was observed in the parenchymatic-adapted clones. Our study demonstrates that stem-to-leaf migration plays an important role in Cm virulence, which may require a phase shift between vascular and parenchymatic

Investigating the defensive roles of cuticular lipids in wild, landrace and domesticated barley during the interaction with the brown rust fungus *Puccinia hordei*

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Barley domestication occurred 8,000 years ago in the fertile crescent, and nowadays it ranks as the 4th most important agricultural crop globally. Extensive research has explored the impact of domestication on barley cultivation, yet little is known about its effects on the biosynthetic pathways leading to the formation of the leaf cuticle layer, which plays key roles during plant development and plant-pathogen interaction. Herein, we investigated variations in the morphology and chemical composition of epicuticular waxes among wild, landrace, and domesticated barley cultivars via scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) analyses. SEM revealed variations in wax density patterns, though no clear correlation was found between genotypes and wax density. GC-MS profiling identified four main wax biochemical classes: fatty acids, alcohols, *n*-alkanes and phytosterols, in which total wax loads correlated with SEM observations. Previously, epicuticular waxes were shown to greatly shape plant-pathogen interactions, and consequently we sought to explore whether the differential leaf wax profiles affect the interactions with *Puccinia hordei*, the causal agent of barley brown rust disease. To this end, we are now performing a series of *in vivo* and *in vitro* inoculation experiments to reveal the effects of wax variations and specific wax components on fungal pathogenicity and pre-penetration capacities. The results of this study are likely to shed light on the impact of domestication processes on the structure and chemical composition of barley leaf waxes and their roles during plant-fungal interactions.

Combining Precise Fertilization and Autumn Gibberellin for Increased Yield and Reduced inflorescence dieback in Avocado

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High levels of phosphorus (P) fertilization increase flowering in Hass avocado but also cause inflorescence and shoot dieback. Various pathogens, from the Botryosphaeria family and *Colletotrichum spp.*, are associated with this phenomenon. Existing fungicides are not effective enough, necessitating improved management practices. Applying gibberellin (GA) in the autumn has been examined in recent years and found to improve yield and increase the ratio of vegetative (indeterminate) inflorescences. Research objectives: To examine the relationship between increased P fertilization levels and inflorescence dieback and to explore methods to reduce infection by applying fungicides in the spring and GA in the autumn. Our results showed that (i) High P fertilization increased the number of determinate inflorescences and the incidence of dieback. (ii) GA treatment had the opposite effect of fertilization, significantly reducing the rate of infested inflorescences and, correspondingly, reducing the number of determinate inflorescences, while increasing the number of fruit sets by factor of 5.6. Treatment with Uniconazole (anti-gibberellin) reduced yields and increased the number of determinate inflorescences. (iii) Copper treatment during flowering doubled the fruit set and yields. Thus, we conclude that high P fertilization increases the rate of determinate inflorescences and therefore increases the tree's sensitivity to dieback. Additional pathogens, besides Botryosphaeria, may cause the phenomenon, as seen in the Jordan Valley and at Gilat Farm where *Colletotrichum spp.* and other fungi were identified. Applying GA in autumn can reduce dieback even with high fertilization, likely due to increased vegetative inflorescences. Further research is needed to confirm these findings.

***trans*-2-Octenal controls *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *lycopersici*, the causal agent of tomato wilt *in vitro*, in soil and in the field**

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Fungal plant diseases cause major crop losses. Phytopathogenic fungi's ability to evolve resistance to fungicides, alongside their ongoing prohibition by the European Commission because of the pronounced adverse effects they have on human health and the environment, make their control a challenge. Moreover, development of less perilous fungicides is a complex task. Here we describe the process and challenges involved in the development of a novel fungicide, from *in-vitro* studies to field experiments. *In-vitro* experiments with *trans*-2-octenal, a bioactive compound secreted by the endophytic fungus *Daldinia* cf. *concentrica*, revealed its ability to fully inhibit and kill phytopathogenic microorganisms. A formulated version of *trans*-2-octenal was then used against the soil-borne pathogen *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *lycopersici* (Forl), the causal agent of tomato vascular wilt disease, in pot experiments with different soil types. We found the highest fungicidal activity in sandy and loam soils, whereas heavy soil impaired activity. Lastly, we investigated the activity of the formulated *trans*-2-octenal against Forl in semi-field experiments. We achieved complete elimination of Forl, provided the soil is rotavated after *trans*-2-octenal application. Taken together, *trans*-2-octenal has the potential to control Forl *in vitro*, in pots and in the field.

Endoplasmic Reticulum (ER) - associated molecular interactions of *Liberibacter solanacearum* with its carrot psyllid vector

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Candidatus *Liberibacter solanacearum* (CLso) haplotype D is a phloem-restricted gram negative plant pathogenic bacterium and transmitted by the carrot psyllid *Bactericera trigonica* in a persistent and propagative mode, and causes the carrot yellows disease. Our previous studies confirmed that the expression of key genes in the ER-associated protein degradation (ERAD), were upregulated in CLso infected psyllids, suggesting induced ER stress. Prolonged ER stress, induces the unfolded protein response (UPR) which lies in the basis of orchestrated signaling pathways leading to the activation of apoptosis. Here we investigated the involvement of UPR in the interactions with CLso and its role in the observed induced apoptosis. By quantifying the expression of UPR and apoptosis related genes using qRT-PCR, testing a key UPR protein (PERK) expression and activity using immunostaining and investigating PERK's expression profile after using chemical ER stressors, we found that apoptosis is indeed induced in *B. trigonica* as a result of CLso infection. CLso affect the expression of PERK in the psyllids midgut and it significantly changes the expression profile of PERK in case of chemical induction of ER stress. These results suggest that the PERK pathway and UPR are putatively involved in the apoptosis observed as an immune response to CLso infection. While the precise mechanisms remain to be elucidated, this study provides critical insights into the interactions between ER stress, UPR, and CLso in psyllids, paving the way for alternative management strategies for *Liberibacter*-associated plant diseases.

Adaptation of the Fungus *Alternaria atra* from Biological Soil Crusts to Extreme Environmental Conditions

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Fungi of the genus *Alternaria* cause plant diseases, including in desert plants, yet little is known about their activity and survival mechanisms in soil without a host. Studies indicate these fungi can endure drought and heat. Biological soil crusts (BSCs), which cover many desert soils, harbor microorganisms that have evolved unique resistance strategies to withstand desiccation, radiation, and high temperatures. Water supply in BSCs depends mainly on dew, making the ability to endure daily cycles of drying and rewetting essential for survival. *Alternaria atra* is one of the dominant fungal species in BSCs. To understand how it thrives, we characterized its optimal growth conditions. Preliminary data show that *A. atra* survives and even develops during wet–dry cycles. Moreover, its highest growth rate occurs at 25 °C under low salt and glycerol concentrations. These findings suggest that, while *A. atra* tolerates extreme drought and heat in a desiccated state, it grows best under more moderate conditions—typical of cooler nights when dew is available. It remains unknown whether this capacity to grow in soil without a host—by exploiting dew and readily available nutrients—extends to other fungal species. A deeper understanding of such persistence strategies will guide the development of more efficient, environmentally friendly soil-disinfestation methods.

Exploring *Chlorella ohadii*, a green alga isolated from the Negev desert for sustainable biological control of soil-borne diseases.

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The use of biological control agents (BCAs) to reduce the use of chemical pesticides is one of the promising solutions toward sustainable agriculture. Nevertheless, the complex interaction of these agents with their biotic and abiotic environment challenges the development of novel, effective agents. Utilizing a highly resilient BCA coupled with a better understanding of the influence of environmental conditions on its antimicrobial activity may increase the chances of successful implementation of the BCA in the field. A green alga isolated from desert biological soil crusts shows a remarkable ability to withstand harsh environmental conditions. Preliminary results show that this alga significantly inhibits the growth, viability, and melanin production of several pathogenic fungi. Among these, *Rhizoctonia solani* was selected as a model for this study due to its susceptibility. Our results demonstrated that varying salinity, carbon source concentrations, light and temperature levels impact the antifungal activity of the alga. Notably, the addition of 0.2M NaCl to the growth medium significantly enhances its antifungal effect, suppressing growth and melanin production.

Building on these findings, this study aims to examine the ability of the microalga to inhibit the pathogenic activity of *R. solani* in planta and to better understand the mechanism of inhibition of the antifungal compounds. In parallel, we are trying to isolate and characterize the antifungal compound. This research seeks to advance our understanding of algae-fungi interactions in the soil, and the influence of environmental conditions on this interaction. Ultimately, this will allow the successful implementation of sustainable solutions for managing soil-borne pathogenic fungi.

Exploring Premature Field collapse during late growth stage in Spring Session potatoes in the western Negev, Israel

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Potato cultivation in the Western Negev of Israel is encountering an increased in premature field collapse during the late growth stages at the spring season, resulting in significant crop damage and yield reduction. The early stages of this phenomenon are marked by necrotic spots on the leaves, resembling symptoms caused by *Alternaria* spp. and/or magnesium deficiency. However, within less than two weeks, atypical withering leads to a rapid collapse of all plants in the plot, which cannot be controlled even with the application of synthetic fungicides. This project seeks to investigate the underlying cause of this phenomenon. In vitro screening of *A. alternata*, extracted from symptomatic potato plants, revealed different level of sensitivity to commonly used fungicides. These isolates exhibited reduced sensitivity to odion, polar, and amister fungicides recording average ED50 of 104.4385, 196.934, and 129.7308 ppm respectively. A greenhouse nutrient wash trial demonstrated that plant collapse occurred across various levels of magnesium application. Moreover, foliar infection levels increased even at optimal magnesium concentrations, indicating that the phenomenon is not related with magnesium deficiency. Another greenhouse experiment revealed that necrotic spots on potato foliage appeared 55 days after planting following artificial inoculation with *A. alternata*. However, these necrotic symptoms did not lead to plant collapse. Similarly, artificial inoculation of potato seedlings with suspected bacterial isolates cultured from rotten stolons failed to reproduce symptoms associated with premature field collapse. Hence, the exact cause of the phenomenon remains unknown and requires further investigations to design appropriate management strategies.